

CHARACTERISTICS OF RELIABILITY OF 20 KV ELECTRICAL NETWORK ELEMENTS

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***Annotation.** This article discusses the reliability characteristics of 20 kV electrical network elements, including power lines, transformer substations and switching devices. This emphasizes the importance of these components in ensuring the efficient and safe operation of energy systems. The study analyzes factors that affect the reliability of 20 kV networks, such as environmental impact, installation quality and Human Factors.*

***Keywords:** Transformer Substations, Switching Devices, Environmental Factors, Human Factors.*

***Аннотация.** В данной статье рассматриваются характеристики надежности элементов электрической сети 20 кВ, включая линии электропередачи, трансформаторные подстанции и коммутационные аппараты. Это подчеркивает важность этих компонентов для обеспечения эффективной и безопасной работы энергетических систем. В исследовании анализируются факторы, влияющие на надежность сетей 20 кВ, такие как воздействие на окружающую среду, качество монтажа и человеческий фактор.*

***Ключевые слова:** трансформаторные подстанции, коммутационные аппараты, факторы окружающей среды, человеческий фактор,*

The reliability of electrical systems is a crucial factor for ensuring the efficient and safe operation of energy systems. The main elements of a 20 kV electrical

network are power transmission lines, transformer substations, and switching devices. The reliability of each of these elements directly affects the overall reliability of the system. Among these, power transmission lines are the weakest element of the 20 kV electrical network.

In relatively newly designed 20 kV voltage electrical networks, grounding through a neutral low-resistance resistor significantly reduces switching voltage, decreases the requirements placed on the cable line screens, and ensures selective action of protective currents in the event of a single-phase short circuit. Several principles are taken into account in the initial stages of constructing a 20 kV electrical network:

- The design of 20 kV power transmission networks utilizes two-section distribution points that automatically connect to two regional separated power centers—110-220/20 kV substations.
- The 20 kV distribution network is constructed using a two-bus scheme connected to two power centers, where each transformer substation is linked via two mutually protected cable lines of 20/0.4 kV.

The electrical supply and distribution networks of 20 kV are formed using interconnected polyethylene-insulated cables. The reliability of electrical networks is the most influential factor throughout their life cycle. Therefore, the task of analyzing how the listed characteristics of 20 kV electrical networks affect the reliability characteristics of their elements is set forth. The article examines which parameters of the 20 kV electrical network elements influence the reliability characteristics of Uzbekistan's energy systems. In a 20 kV electrical network, cable lines are used to transmit electricity over distances of several dozen kilometers, and they possess several characteristics that may affect their reliability. For instance, various environmental factors, such as temperature, humidity, and mechanical loads, can influence the cables. Additionally, cables may suffer damage due to non-

compliance with technological standards during installation or operation.

Moreover, to enhance the reliability of electrical systems, it is essential to consider not only the parameters of cable lines but also other factors, such as the quality of equipment, working conditions, and the qualifications of operating personnel, as well as system maintenance. Regular technical inspections and diagnostics of equipment are also important for identifying potential problems and preventing emergencies. According to obtained statistical data, the distribution of organizational and technical causes of cable line failures is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of Causes for Cable Line Failures

Organizational reasons for failure of cable lines:			
installation defects 37.5%;	unclassified causes 3.1%;	unknown causes 21.9%.	influence of unauthorized persons 37.5%;
The main technical reasons for cable line accidents are as follows:			
electric arc damage 59.4%	loss in Rust 3,1%.	external mechanical impact 37,5%	

Additionally, based on statistical data regarding faults in 20 kV cable lines, it has been shown that the number of incidents is significantly lower compared to three-core cables with paper-oil insulation at 6-10 kV voltage levels. As for the organizational causes of failures in 20 kV networks, it has been determined that a significant proportion is attributed to the "human factor," including the influence of unauthorized individuals, installation defects, and the lack of qualifications among maintenance personnel, among other issues.

Switching equipment plays a crucial role in modern 20 kV electrical networks. High-voltage circuit breakers and reclosers are the primary switching devices in 20 kV electrical networks. Studies on the parameters of switching processes in 20 kV high-voltage circuit breakers indicate that the quality of switching depends on several factors.

According to the obtained statistical indicators, the failure rate for 10 kV oil circuit breakers is $\omega = 0.009$ per year. In contrast, the failure rate for modern 20 kV distribution circuit breakers (vacuum and gas-insulated) is $\omega = 0.002$ per year. This indicates that the reliability of modern 20 kV distribution circuit breakers is significantly higher. The grounding modes of the neutral and, consequently, the switching voltage levels in these networks are considered potential primary causes of failures in the examined devices.

In medium-voltage networks, the feasibility of transitioning from an extended system with nominal voltages of 110/6-10-20-35 kV to a reduced 110/20 kV system has been proposed in several other articles. In overhead networks, the 110/20 kV system, directly transformed to 20/0.4 kV, requires significantly less funding, fewer colored metals, and especially transformer power across a wide range of load density.

The analysis of the technical and economic indicators of transformer substations shows that the technical and economic characteristics of a packaged transformer substation at 35/0.4 kV and a transformer substation at 20/0.4 kV are, if not equal, then in some cases very close. Table 3 provides an example of the aggregated cost indicators for a packaged transformer substation at a high-capacity plant for 35/0.4 kV and a somewhat similar 20/0.4 kV transformer substation.

Table 2. Cumulative indicators of the cost of a transformer substation, mln.sum

Kuchlanish U_{nom} , kV	Quvvat S_{nom} , kVA				
	100	160	250	400	630
20/0,4	144	152	176	194	247
35/0,4	182	184	191	198	263

For the transformer substation in Table 2, the electrical connection schemes on the 20 kV and 35 kV sides are identical: a disconnecter and fuses are installed at the input to protect the power transformer. The no-load losses and short-circuit losses

of 20/0.4 kV and 35/0.4 kV transformers with equal nominal power are very similar and will not be considered further.

The identified failure rate for 6(10)/0.4 kV transformer substations is $\omega = 0.006$ per year. In contrast, the identified failure rate for 20/0.4 kV voltage transformers is $\omega = 0.0014$ per year. Compared to this figure, the failure rate for new 20/0.4 kV voltage transformers is five times lower.

Utilizing 20 kV voltage in the existing 6-10 kV distribution networks allows consumers in Uzbekistan to achieve a higher level of electricity supply, increasing capacity compared to existing networks, reducing technological losses, and improving the quality of electrical energy, energy security, and the reliability of electricity supply systems.

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